
Responsible AI Needs Neural Constraints, Not Just Post-Hoc Governance

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Abstract

This position paper argues that responsible AI cannot be achieved via post-hoc governance, model cards, or behavioral alignment alone. It must also be designed around measurable constraints on efficiency, auditability, robustness, and human oversight. We propose that neuroscience offers a principled source of such constraints through two complementary lenses. The instrumental lens imports brain-derived design priors - sparsity, event-driven computation, local learning, modular routing, dendritic computation, and neuromorphic substrates - to improve efficiency and governability. The epistemic lens adapts neuroscience tools for studying opaque biological systems, including representational geometry, topology, and cognitive stress tests, to make AI systems more legible, contestable, and accountable without requiring complete mechanistic decomposition. We operationalize this agenda through a minimal benchmark suite that pairs energy and CO_2e audits with representation audits, robustness probes, and cognitive bias tests, and through deployment patterns for abstention, deferral, oversight logging, and event-driven edge computation. Rather than treating the brain as a template to copy, we argue that neuroscience should serve as a source of falsifiable design hypotheses for building AI systems that are capable, sustainable, and accountable by design.

1 Introduction

As AI systems become embedded in social, economic, political, and scientific life, the need for responsible AI has become increasingly urgent. Calls for responsible development, deployment, and governance from organizations such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the EU AI Act emphasize fairness, transparency and explainability, accountability, technical robustness and safety, privacy, alignment with human values, and societal and environmental well-being. In practice, these principles require systems with human-in-the-loop oversight and clear accountability; governed, privacy-preserving data; transparent documentation and explanations; robustness, security, and fairness across populations, noise, and adversarial attacks; continuous lifecycle risk management; and optimization for energy efficiency and societal benefit.

Yet the current trajectory of AI development often conflicts with these goals. Modern AI systems are increasingly large, data-hungry, compute-intensive, and opaque. Three failures are especially salient. First, large-scale AI models remain black boxes whose internal mechanisms and decision processes are often opaque even to their creators, making auditing and contestation structurally difficult [Lipton, 2018, Rudin, 2019]. Foundation models in particular exhibit failure modes that even developers cannot reliably predict [Bommasani et al., 2021]. Second, they are ecologically costly. Training a single large model with neural architecture search can emit CO_2 equivalent to five cars over their

lifetimes [Strubell et al., 2019], while the field’s incentive structure continues to reward accuracy gains regardless of compute cost [Schwartz et al., 2020]. Without tools to monitor societal and environmental footprint, responsible oversight remains difficult. Third, models trained on massive internet-scale datasets can absorb biased, stereotyped, or harmful representations. Standard models trained on web text reproduce human implicit biases measured by the Implicit Association Test [Caliskan et al., 2017], and at internet scale no curation process can identify and remove all biased content before training begins [Bender et al., 2021]. Without explicit correction or calibration, such biases become embedded and amplified in AI outputs. These failures are not hypothetical risks, but measurable documented costs that existing approaches (e.g., model cards, efficiency benchmarks, post-training alignment) have not yet resolved at scale.

Position: *Responsible AI cannot be achieved by post-hoc governance, model cards, RLHF, or accuracy-only benchmarks alone. It requires design-time constraints and representation-level audits. Neuroscience provides a principled source of both.* We do not propose neuroscience as a replacement for existing responsible-AI approaches, but as a complementary set of design and evaluation priors. Responsible-AI goals serve as the selection criterion for which biological principles are relevant. Those principles in turn instantiate measurable engineering targets, such as energy-per-inference, representational stability, robustness under distribution shift. This framework unifies goals and constraints because the selection criterion and the instantiation are the same act. Within this, we argue for a nuanced approach where biological inspiration and plausibility are not a panacea and the brain is not a glorified entity to be mimicked, but rather a rich source of design principles and theoretical insights that can guide the creation of more accountable AI systems. We develop this argument through two routes: an instrumental route, where biological plausibility offers concrete heuristics for improving energy efficiency, robustness, interpretability, transparency, and explainability; and an epistemic route, where neuroscience provides tools for studying and auditing complex opaque systems.

Roadmap: This paper develops four main contributions across the indicated sections. First, we introduce a two-lens framework for neuro-inspired responsible AI: an instrumental lens that imports brain-derived efficiency and governability priors (Section 3) and an epistemic lens that applies representational geometry and topology for legibility and auditability (Section 4). Second, we propose a minimal benchmark suite that pairs energy/ CO_2e audits with representation audits, cognitive stress tests, and standardized reporting, turning the two lenses into measurable evaluation criteria (Section 5). Third, we present the visual cortex as a worked case study showing how these benchmarks can be instantiated through concrete metrics and deployment patterns for robustness, auditability, and energy efficiency (Section 6). Fourth, we offer a call to action specifying a three-part transfer criterion, interdisciplinary collaboration mechanisms, and a research outlook agenda (Section 8). The appendix tables provide a structured index linking each neurobiological feature to its responsible-AI principle and reportable metric.

Figure 1: A brain-inspired pipeline for responsible AI: brain-derived priors improve efficiency and governability; representational audits support legibility and contestability.

2 The Allure and Ambiguity of Brain-Inspired AI

Taking inspiration from the brain is not new: artificial neural networks (ANNs) were themselves loosely inspired by biological neurons and neural networks [Hebb, 2005, McCulloch and Pitts, 1943, Rosenblatt, 1958, Rumelhart et al., 1986]. From early perceptrons [Rosenblatt, 1958] to convolutional neural networks [LeCun et al., 2002], biological metaphors have long shaped AI models (Section 6). Today, this impulse is increasingly formalized in NeuroAI, which seeks to align brain-inspired architectures with computational principles of neural systems [Zador et al., 2023]. Spiking neural networks (SNNs), recurrent architectures, local learning algorithms, and neuromorphic hardware are

all being explored as routes toward more brain-like systems. Funding initiatives such as the Human Brain Project, the BRAIN Initiative, NeuroAI programs at institutions such as Princeton, Cold Spring Harbor, and UCL, and industrial efforts by Intel, IBM, and Google DeepMind further signal growing institutional commitment to this agenda.

Yet biological plausibility remains an ambiguous objective. What does it mean for a system to be brain-like: architectural similarity, functional resemblance, behavioral parity, or something else? Without clear definitions, brain inspiration risks becoming a virtue signal or a deflection from unresolved concerns about explainability, scalability, and fairness. To avoid uncritical biological essentialism, we argue for a functionalist framing: brain-inspired anatomical and computational features should be adopted only when they demonstrably advance responsible-AI objectives. In this framework, two lenses contribute to responsible AI (**Fig. 1**). The first is an instrumental lens, in which the brain serves as a source of heuristics and computational constraints for building systems that are more efficient, robust, interpretable, and governable. Here, the brain is not a template to copy, but a source of testable design priors.

The second is an epistemic lens, in which neuroscience offers tools for studying opaque, adaptive systems without requiring complete mechanistic understanding. This does not mean treating the brain as rational, fair, or optimal. Brains, like ANNs, rely on heuristics, make biased decisions, and often optimize for utility rather than truth. Precisely for this reason, understanding the limits and mechanisms of human cognition can help calibrate AI systems not merely to mimic the brain, but to avoid its flaws [Binz and Schulz, 2023, Hagendorff et al., 2023]. We can learn from sources of bias identified in perception and decision-making [Caliskan et al., 2017, Bender et al., 2021], from heuristic shortcuts that trade accuracy for efficiency, and from context-sensitive representations that encode social priors. More broadly, neuroscience provides paradigms for probing non-transparent, high-dimensional, dynamic systems such as brains and ANNs, making it a source not only of design inspiration but also of audit methodology.

3 The Instrumental Lens: Energy Efficiency, Governability from the Brain

One of the strongest arguments for biological plausibility is energy efficiency. The human brain consumes roughly 20 watts—less than a typical laptop—while supporting sensory integration, continual learning, long-term memory, abstract reasoning, and adaptive behavior. This contrasts sharply with large language models such as ChatGPT, which require thousands of GPUs, extensive data-center cooling, and can consume 300,000 kg of CO_2 for model training alone [Patterson et al., 2021].

How does the brain achieve this frugality, and what can AI learn from it? Several features already function as engineering levers for efficient and governable systems (see Tables 2 and 3 for features, responsibility payoffs, and reportable metrics, and Table 1 for corresponding governance artifacts). 1) *Sparse activity*: only a small subset of neurons is active at any moment, reducing energy use and increasing information efficiency [Wang et al., 2020]. 2) *Event-driven computation*: neurons fire only when needed; spiking neural networks (SNNs) model this behavior and reduce redundant operations [Cao et al., 2015, Nazari and Amiri, 2025]. 3) *Local learning*: biological learning rules are local and asynchronous, motivating Hebbian learning, spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP), and feedback alignment [Bengio et al., 2015, Lv et al., 2024]. 4) *Low-precision signaling*: neural signals are analog and approximate, avoiding the cost of high-precision digital computation. 5) *Redundancy reduction*: prediction-error signals minimize data transfer by measuring the discrepancy between expectation and reality [Marblestone et al., 2016]. Predictive coding frameworks approximate error backpropagation through local Hebbian plasticity [Whittington and Bogacz, 2017] and can support more efficient synaptic updates during learning [Song et al., 2024].

These are not merely metaphors. Brain-inspired mechanisms have already produced measurable efficiency gains. 6) *Dendritic computation*: biological neurons use dendrites for local nonlinear operations, enabling reduced energy use and improved generalization in deep networks, while matching standard accuracy with fewer parameters [Chavlis and Poirazi, 2025] [Pagkalos et al., 2024]. 7) *Microcircuit architecture*: neuro-inspired modularity, hierarchical connectivity, and local routing can support both scalability and efficiency [Schuman et al., 2022]. 8) *Neuromorphic hardware*: platforms such as Intel’s Loihi demonstrate efficient online learning with SNNs, using far less energy than traditional hardware [Greatorex et al., 2025, Schuman et al., 2022] and achieving $100\times-1,000\times$ energy reductions over conventional processors [Davies et al., 2021]. Together, these results show that

neuroscience-derived priors can yield reportable efficiency gains, directly addressing sustainability and governability.

Paradox and Promise: Is Efficiency Enough? Energy efficiency alone, however, does not guarantee sustainability. As AI systems become cheaper to deploy, they can invite broader and more frequent use, increasing aggregate environmental impact. This is a form of the Jevons Paradox, where efficiency gains lead to increased consumption [Alcott, 2005]. For instance, lower per-query inference costs have enabled ChatGPT-scale systems to serve billions of requests daily, raising questions about how, where, and when such systems should be used. Efficiency can therefore become a moral hazard if it enables frictionless overuse without accountability.

Biological plausibility also carries its own costs. Training SNNs, dendritic models, or other biologically motivated architectures may require specialized hardware and careful optimization. Without careful design, systems can become biologically plausible in form but computationally costly in practice. Still, biologically inspired research remains strategically valuable because it offers a dual payoff: better AI models and better computational accounts of brain function. This synergy can prioritize designs that are efficient, modular, and adaptable, even when they do not maximize accuracy benchmarks. A related challenge is Sutton’s “Bitter Lesson”, which argues that scaling with general-purpose algorithms has historically outperformed hand-crafted inductive biases, including neuroscience-inspired ones, on accuracy benchmarks [Sutton, 2019]. Our claim is narrower: we target responsible-AI properties where neuroscience-derived priors provide measurable gains that scaling alone does not replicate [Davies et al., 2021, Dapello et al., 2020, Chavlis and Poirazi, 2025].

Such models may not replace large foundation models, but they are especially relevant for responsible, embedded, and sustainable AI. Smart sensors and mobile devices require low-latency, low-power models that operate without constant connectivity. Similar constraints arise in wildlife tracking, climate sensing, and conservation technology, where energy availability, intermittent connectivity, and ecological disturbance matter. Because these systems are often operated by non-ML experts, interpretability, explainability, and transparency become essential for trust, safety, and accountability. The same concerns apply to AI in health, education, brain-computer interfaces, and prosthetics, where real-time, interpretable, and safe algorithms must align with green-computing and regulatory goals.

Responsibility also depends on how models are integrated into human workflows. Here, cognitive neuroscience can inform interface design and deployment. Findings on bounded rationality and neural speed-accuracy trade-offs motivate operator-set thresholds, such as “fast” versus “sure” modes, and calibrated abstain/needs-review states [Bogacz, 2007]. Working-memory limits and attentional blink motivate progressive disclosure, chunked outputs, and attention-aware timing so assistance arrives when users can process it [Cowan, 2001, Raymond et al., 1992, Sweller, 1988]. Dopaminergic reward-prediction error cautions against variable-ratio, “sticky” UX patterns and instead supports feedback that rewards high-value, low-energy behavior, such as per-task energy/ CO_2 nudges; [Schultz et al., 1997]. Predictive-coding principles further favor event-driven edge deployments that “wake on surprise” and interfaces that highlight deviations from baseline rather than full reports, saving energy while focusing human attention [Friston, 2010].

Thus, true responsibility requires more than efficient models. It also requires intentional deployment frameworks, user-aware design, and regulatory scaffolding. Neuroscience contributes not only energy-efficient design priors, but also insight into bounded rationality, cognitive overload, and adaptive learning, enabling human-AI systems that encourage frugal, meaningful use rather than frictionless overuse.

4 The Epistemic Lens: Interpretability Beyond Mechanistic Decomposition

An important part of creating responsible AI is to develop and deploy systems that are transparent, interpretable, and explainable. While transparency involves disclosing the model’s data, training, deployment, and ownership, explainability is focused on understanding the model’s reasoning and decision-making. But as Henderson and colleagues [Henderson et al., 2020] argue, transparency does not guarantee understandability. Interpretability is therefore needed to connect disclosure and explanation by making the system’s internal behavior legible. The dominant approach has often been mechanistic analysis: identifying neurons, weights, or circuits that causally implement a behavior by tracing and testing flows from input to output [Olah et al., 2020]. A canonical example is the discovery

of “induction heads” in transformers, attention-head pairs that implement next-token copying by attending from a repeated token to its previous occurrence, enabling a simple form of in-context learning [Olsson et al., 2022]. Ablation and activation patching provide causal evidence for this circuit. Yet mechanistic analysis faces diminishing returns as model size grows. Even identifying induction heads—a two-component circuit in small transformers—required substantial effort [Olsson et al., 2022], and no comparable mechanistic accounts exist for production-scale models despite far greater researcher effort. Just as tracing individual spikes rarely explains cognition, inspecting individual weights may reveal little about overall model behavior.

Neuroscience offers a complementary strategy: interpretability through internal representations. In brains and ANNs, causal model representations are partly implicit in learning and neural activity, and therefore cannot be cleanly dissociated from them [Caglar and Hanson, 2017]. Despite persistent microscopic opacity, neuroscience has developed tools for mapping how information is encoded and transformed across layers, populations, and levels of analysis. These tools map population codes, analyze high-dimensional representations on low-dimensional manifolds, and characterize geometric and topological structure. For example, moving from single neurons to population codes revealed mixed selectivity: neurons simultaneously represent multiple unrelated task-relevant features [Rigotti et al., 2013]. This enables populations to embed high-dimensional neural representations in nonlinear subspaces [Fusi et al., 2016]. Neuroscience increasingly uses representational geometry to ask how information is organized in population codes, how dynamics evolve along manifolds, and how topology constrains function. Representational similarity analysis (RSA; [Kriegeskorte et al., 2008]) and its topological variants [Lin and Kriegeskorte, 2024] have been used to compare population-level activity across cortical areas, revealing abstract encoding structures shared across stimuli, tasks, or species, as well as low-dimensional sensory subspaces tuned to task variables or behavioral goals [Gallego et al., 2017].

This shift from single units to population-level structure reflects a practical necessity. As model size grows, tracing individual weights becomes computationally intractable, making geometric structure a scalable legibility signal. Crucially, these tools are not merely descriptive. Centered Kernel Alignment (CKA) used as a pruning criterion achieves $>75\%$ FLOPs reduction on ResNets while improving out-of-distribution (OOD) accuracy [Pons et al., 2024]. CKA has also diagnosed representational misalignment as the mechanism behind model-merging failures and motivated a geometric fix [Stoica et al., 2024]. Similarly, topological cycle matching can detect adversarial vulnerabilities and identify prunable layers [Reani and Bobrowski, 2021, García-Redondo et al., 2024, Gardinazzi et al., 2024, Rieck et al., 2018], while geometric concept vectors enable causal steering interventions [Birdal et al., 2021, Saviotto et al., 2026]. Applied to AI systems, RSA has revealed shared encoding formats between deep networks and primate visual cortex [Kriegeskorte, 2009], and manifold geometry shows how class separation and generalization emerge across network layers [Cohen et al., 2020]. Such representational approaches complement, rather than replace, mechanistic interpretability: geometry identifies *where* structure has failed, while mechanistic analysis identifies *which parameters* to fix.

Representation-level analysis is not new to ML—ANNs have always contained distributed representations [Rumelhart et al., 1986]—but the neuroscience and ML communities have largely developed these tools in parallel, at times independently rediscovering the same concepts. For example, ANNs encode stimulus features in a superposition of linearly overlaid concepts [Elhage et al., 2022], which ML calls “polysemanticity” or “dictionary learning”. The same phenomenon is what neuroscience has called “mixed selectivity” and “sparse coding” for over a decade [Rigotti et al., 2013]. Similarly, CKA [Kornblith et al., 2019] and RSA [Kriegeskorte et al., 2008] were developed in ML and neuroscience respectively and have now been shown to be mathematically equivalent under a squared Euclidean formulation [Williams, 2024]. As two communities working on the same difficult task of understanding a complex neural information processing system, stronger crosstalk is needed between neuroscience and ML to close such terminology gaps, reduce duplicated effort, and accelerate the transfer of interpretability tools in both directions.

Finally, the responsible-AI requirements emphasized here—auditability and human-aligned oversight—have formal analogues in control theory. Observability and controllability, two foundational concepts in control theory [Kalman, 1960], map onto auditability and oversight, respectively. Observability asks whether a system’s internal state can be inferred from its outputs; representational geometry tools such as RSA, CKA, and manifold analysis provide this by making internal structure legible from the outside. Controllability asks whether human intervention can reliably steer system behavior; this maps onto deployment patterns such as abstention and deferral thresholds, modular routing, and

escalation logs. Safety-constrained reinforcement learning and control barrier functions can then provide formal guarantees that complement representation-level audits [Ames et al., 2019].

5 Responsible AI Needs New Benchmarks

Improving model performance is often pursued through scaling: larger models, more data, and greater computational resources. But scaling alone is not a responsible path forward. Current AI benchmarks prioritize predictive accuracy or generation quality, often under narrow conditions with static, unrepresentative data. But responsible AI demands new benchmarks that also evaluate robustness to bias, adaptability to diverse populations, transparency and interpretability of decision-making, and environmental impact. This is where neuroscience and cognitive science offer more than metaphors and can provide guidance in the form of testable design hypotheses and metrics that can be selectively adopted (see Tables 2 and 3 for a comprehensive overview of all features).

Humans are not unbiased agents: we exhibit confirmation bias, anchoring, framing effects, optimism bias, and many other systematic failures. A responsible system should not mirror these flaws but correct or calibrate against them. Concretely, using the cognitive bias literature to design evaluation criteria means models are tested against *known* human failure modes rather than accuracy alone. The stress tests in this section instantiate precisely this approach [Binz and Schulz, 2023, Hagendorff et al., 2023]. Thus, benchmark suites should include “cognitive stress tests” that probe whether models resist human-like pitfalls, and systems should be evaluated for their ability to compensate for, not inherit, human fallibility.

Responsibility metrics should therefore extend beyond task accuracy to include energy audits, representation alignment, bias and fairness assessments, and neuroscience-inspired tests of robustness and legibility. These metrics can include perturbation robustness, modular retrainability, sparsity, and topological stability of internal codes. Some infrastructure already exists: energy can be estimated with AI Energy Score [Luccioni et al., 2025], ML.Energy [Chung et al., 2025], MLPerfPower [Tschand et al., 2025], and environmental-footprint reporting standards [Henderson et al., 2020]; robustness can be evaluated with natural and synthetic perturbation probes such as ImageNet-C/-P/-A [Hendrycks and Dietterich, 2019, Koh et al., 2021] and adversarial tests such as RobustBench [Croce et al., 2020]. What is still missing is a stronger norm for multi-dimensional benchmarks, because responsibility does not scale linearly with parameters. Other neuroscience-inspired benchmarks could include measures of topological stability tracked via persistent-homology metrics such as Neural Persistence before and after fine-tuning [Rieck et al., 2018] or measures of modular retrainability by reporting how localized an edit is using subspace and weight-edit workflows such as Iterative Nullspace Projection (INLP) [Ravfogel et al., 2020] and Rank-One Model Editing (ROME) [Meng et al., 2022]).

Cognitive stress tests rooted in neuroscience and cognitive science should also be included to ensure that models avoid human-like failure modes while supporting users. These could include measures of 1) framing invariance: stable recommendations under gain/loss rewordings [Tversky and Kahneman, 1981], already documented as a failure mode in GPT-family models [Binz and Schulz, 2023, Hagendorff et al., 2023]; 2) anchoring resilience: resistance to irrelevant numeric anchors [Tversky and Kahneman, 1974], likewise demonstrated in large language models [Binz and Schulz, 2023]; 3) confirmation-challenge: propensity to retrieve disconfirming evidence rather than echo the user’s prior [Nickerson, 1998]; 4) calibration & abstention: well-calibrated probabilities and willingness to defer under ambiguity [Kepecs and Mainen, 2012, Geifman and El-Yaniv, 2017]; 5) resource-rational interaction: adaptation to bounded rationality via speed–accuracy modes and progressive disclosure [Bogacz, 2007, Lieder and Griffiths, 2020, Ratcliff, 1978]; and 6) developmental priors/compositionality: few-shot generalization and recombination beyond memorization [Lake et al., 2017]. Finally, behavior-level scores should be coupled with representation-level audits (RSA/CKA drift, manifold separability/geometric changes) so apparent robustness is not bought by fragile, spurious codes. For linear probes, CKA and centered RSA coincide up to scaling, which is why we use them interchangeably as representation-geometry audits. Together, these ingredients would turn “accuracy-only” leaderboards into responsibility benchmarks that measure energy, bias, robustness, interpretability, and human-compatible use.

The instrumental lens constrains design before any benchmark is run: sparsity reduces unnecessary multiply–accumulate operations, event-driven loops wake compute on change, and modular routing

localizes updates. Evaluation should match that design intent. Accordingly, energy per 1k inferences, CO_2e with hardware disclosure, and memory/KV-cache footprints should be reported alongside accuracy, placing efficiency and governability on the same scoreboard.

The epistemic lens complements this by asking how internal codes evolve under fine-tuning and edits. Layer-wise RSA/CKA drift, separability margins, and simple topological stability scores make these changes legible. Coupling these representation audits with cognitive stress tests (anchoring, framing, confirmation-challenge, calibration/abstention) turns accuracy-only leader boards into responsibility benchmarks (see Tables 2 and 3).

6 Case Study: Visual Cortex as an Operational Template

This case study instantiates the two-lens framework in a concrete domain, showing how neuroscience-derived architectural priors can jointly improve robustness, auditability, and energy efficiency. The visual cortex processes images through a hierarchical, topographically organized pathway that has long inspired computer vision. Early areas (V1/V2) extract low-level band-passed features such as edges, contrast, and orientation within local receptive fields, while downstream areas (V4/IT) build increasingly invariant object representations [Carandini and Heeger, 2012, DiCarlo et al., 2012]. These computations are supported by recurrent and feedback connectivity within and across cortical layers [Gilbert and Li, 2013, Lamme and Roelfsema, 2000]. Thus, visual cortex is useful not simply as an origin story for CNNs, but as an operational template for building vision systems that behave well under constraint.

Visual neuroscience suggests three transferable design principles. First, early feature processing should be robust and biologically grounded: V1-like front ends with oriented band-pass filters, gain control, and modest neuronal noise can anchor low-level representations and harden models against corruptions. Second, ambiguous inputs such as clutter or occlusion call for recurrence and top-down feedback, allowing hypotheses to be iteratively refined rather than collapsed into overconfident logits. Third, visual systems should compose scenes from reusable parts and relations, supporting predictable generalization and localized edits.

Robustness. A V1-like front end (Gabor banks, simple/complex pooling, modest neuronal noise) placed before a standard CNN improves alignment with macaque V1 and increases robustness to common corruptions and some white-box attacks without adversarial training [Dapello et al., 2020]. Training that increases shape bias shifts models toward human-like global form cues, improving OOD performance and reducing reliance on non-robust features (e.g. Stylized-ImageNet [Geirhos et al., 2022, Ilyas et al., 2019]). Recurrence further addresses classic feed-forward failure modes such as occlusion and clutter by supporting iterative hypothesis testing and completion of perceptually ambiguous parts [Kar et al., 2019]. More broadly, object-centric and slot-based encodings, structured decoders, and scene graphs extend this cortical logic toward compositional generalization, where novel recombinations behave predictably and small knowledge edits remain local.

Auditability. Cortex-inspired stage-wise processing yields intermediate representations that can be probed with representational similarity analysis (RSA) or Brain-Score to verify neural alignment and track regression after model edits [Cichy and Kaiser, 2019, Schrimpf et al., 2018]. Human active perception, including saccades and foveation, also motivates explicit records of where and when a model looked: glimpse networks and spatial transformers produce focus trajectories that can be logged for review and contestability [Jaderberg et al., 2015, Mnih et al., 2014]. Population-code uncertainty supports calibrated outputs and safe abstention under ambiguity [Knill and Pouget, 2004, Ma et al., 2006]. Finally, retinal event-driven encoding motivates event cameras and neuromorphic front ends that compute on change, reducing latency and energy in edge safety loops [Lichtsteiner et al., 2008].

In this framing, predictive coding becomes an engineering regime rather than a metaphor. Edge systems can remain mostly quiescent, monitor prediction error, log the triggering change and reason code when a threshold is crossed, and only then escalate to a larger model. This event-driven loop converts energy savings into measurable responsibility gains: lower CO_2e per case, reproducible escalation traces, and maintained accuracy on high-value cases.

Active perception and working-memory limits. Biological vision is active, sequential, and resource-bounded. Glimpse policies and chunked context windows make attention auditable, expose resource-

rational trade-offs such as “fast” versus “sure” modes, and create natural points for abstention when the information budget is exhausted. Because processing is stage-wise and routed, intermediate states remain probe-able through RSA/CKA alignment, and the model’s focus trajectory becomes a first-class artifact for post-hoc review in safety-critical use.

Real-world applications. In medical imaging, V1-front-ended or shape-biased models retain better accuracy in low-dose and blur settings [Dapello et al., 2020] while providing confidence ratings for clinician override. In autonomous and aerial robotics, recurrent and event-driven architectures can maintain detection under rainy, foggy, or rapidly changing conditions [Kar et al., 2019] while limiting energy rebound. In conservation camera traps, event pipelines that “wake on surprise,” transmit deltas, and attach human-readable triggers reduce bandwidth and cognitive load. Across these cases, neuro-inspired strategies yield robustness (ImageNet-C/-P/-A), alignment (RSA/Brain-Score), audit trails (focus logs, stage outputs), and efficiency. These metrics operationalize the responsibility framework in Section 5: ImageNet-C/-P/-A deltas map to robustness; RSA/Brain-Score to interpretability and auditability; CO_2e per inference to sustainability; and focus-log completeness to accountability and transparency/contestability. Section 6 therefore serves as a worked instantiation of the full responsibility benchmark suite rather than a collection of examples.

7 Alternative Views

Given the multifaceted nature of our position, we address four alternative views. First, one might argue that the responsible-AI failures motivating this paper are already addressed by model cards, efficiency benchmarks, and RLHF. However, model cards document but do not reduce opacity, efficiency benchmarks are not yet mandatory, and RLHF targets behavioral alignment but not energy consumption, representation drift, or OOD generalization [Bommasani et al., 2021, Strubell et al., 2019, Bender et al., 2021]. The remedies therefore remain incomplete.

Second, “brain-inspired” design may seem unnecessary if governance and standard engineering suffice. Yet substrate-level priors, including energy constraints, representation stability, and edge deployability, address failure modes that behavioral alignment alone cannot reach. A model may pass Constitutional AI-style evaluations while still emitting 300,000 kg CO_2 during training [Patterson et al., 2021] or failing under medical image corruption.

Third, neuroscience analogies can become aesthetic justifications or hard-code human cognitive deficiencies. This is a real danger, and it is why our framework adopts biological principles only as functional hypotheses. Predictive coding, for example, is imported for local updates and reduced data movement, not for the top-down belief propagation that may contribute to confirmation bias. The stress tests in Section 5 are designed to detect whether imported priors introduce such failure modes, making the framework self-correcting.

Finally, representational audits may appear weaker than mechanistic interpretability or formal verification. Our claim, however, is complementarity rather than superiority. Geometry identifies *where* structure has failed, mechanistic analysis identifies *which parameters* to fix, and formal verification provides guarantees neither alone can offer. Brain-derived principles should therefore be treated as falsifiable hypotheses: adopted only when they improve defined responsible-AI metrics and integrated with, not substituted for, governance and adversarial evaluation.

Biological inspiration is not a recipe for AI design. It is a compass: a source of constraints for energy, sparsity, and modularity, and a source of epistemic insight into bias, heuristics, and interpretability. It must also be used with caution, because not all features of the brain are desirable. The goal is not to make AI more biological, but to selectively transfer biological principles that make AI more accountable, interpretable, and sustainable.

8 Call to Action: Turning Lenses into Practice

The near-term agenda is empirical and standardized rather than infrastructural. First, we need to know how much efficiency from sparsity, event-driven triggers, and modular routing survives end-to-end once recurrence, latency, and deployment constraints are included. Editors and reviewers can insist that authors report the same task under a matched “fast” and “sure” setting and disclose the resulting speed–accuracy–energy surface (See Table 1 for an operational example). Second, how local can

Table 1: **From responsible-AI principles to auditable artifacts.** Each principle is paired with a neuro-inspired lever and a concrete artifact that can be included in benchmark reports, supplementary materials, or deployment logs. Unlike Appendix Tables 2 and 3, this table focuses on governance evidence rather than model mechanisms.

Policy principle	Neuro-inspired lever	Artifact to report	Where it lives
Accountability	Modular routing/adapters	Expert-activation traces; edit-locality scores after targeted updates	Deployment logs; public benchmark; publication SM/SI
Transparency/contestability	Stage-wise processing; glimpse/attention	Focus logs, including token spans, image regions, retrieved sources, and intermediate-state snapshots	Deployment logs; publication SM/SI
Human oversight	Abstention/deferral policy	Escalation records with confidence, reason codes, and destination	Deployment logs
Robustness/safety	Event-driven edge loops; recurrence under occlusion	Trigger audits, including time-stamped change events, false-trigger rates, and iterations-to-convergence	Public benchmark; publication SM/SI; deployment
Sustainability	Sparsity; low precision; neuromorphic computation	Energy per inference; CO ₂ e with hardware and precision disclosure	Public benchmark; publication SM/SI
Privacy & data governance	Local learning	Bytes transferred per update; on-device share of learning; DP budget, if used	Publication SM/SI; compliance packet

knowledge edits be in practice? We argue for making representation drift (RSA/CKA and a simple topological stability score) and an edit-locality summary part of routine reporting alongside accuracy. Third, when systems face framing, anchoring, or information overload, what is the right contract with users? Normalizing calibration, abstention/deferral, and auditable focus (what the model consulted and in what order) turns contestability from a narrative into a measurable artifact.

To guide practitioners in applying this framework, we propose a three-part transfer criterion where a neuroscience-derived feature warrants adoption when:

1. it delivers a measurable improvement on a named responsible-AI metric (e.g., energy per inference, robustness score, calibration, edit locality) rather than benchmark accuracy alone;
2. it constitutes a falsifiable hypothesis that can be tested against a matched baseline and rejected if the gain does not materialize;
3. it integrates with rather than replaces governance, mechanistic analysis, or adversarial evaluation.

Two medium-term priorities follow: develop power-constrained credit assignment (e.g., dendritic-style units) as a comparative benchmark goal and standardize energy/CO₂e reporting (hardware, precision, batch shape, and a consistent conversion factor) so results are comparable across labs. None of these require new infrastructure, only for journals and conferences to ask for a small, common set of reportables presented as part of the main claims, not as appendices.

To realize this potential requires close collaboration across disciplines, and we propose three concrete mechanisms to enable it. First, *shared benchmarks with standardized reporting*. The infrastructure already exists in MLPerfPower [Tschand et al., 2025] for energy/CO₂e with hardware and precision disclosure, and AI Energy Score [Luccioni et al., 2025] for inference efficiency, but what is missing is the community norm that these appear in main-paper results, not appendices. Second, *agreed cross-community terminology*, as noted in Section 4, “mixed selectivity” (neuroscience) and “polysemanticity/superposition” (ML) describe the same phenomenon discovered independently; making such mappings explicit in publications and workshops would reduce duplicated effort and accelerate transfer. Third, *joint evaluation tracks*: workshops requiring dual neuroscience-ML evaluation criteria - accuracy on corrupted images alongside RSA alignment to primate neural data - would create incentives for cross-disciplinary design; the Brain-Score benchmarking ecosystem [Schrimpf et al., 2018] provides an existence proof that this is feasible.

Neuroscientists, computer scientists, engineers, lawyers, and policymakers must work together to identify which biological principles translate into scientifically and socially beneficial AI features. In this view, the brain is not a blueprint to copy, but a partner in design: a source of testable constraints for building AI systems that are more responsible by design.

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A Appendix

Table 2: Cognitive/ behavioral features mapped to actionable levers and responsible-AI payoffs. Each row links a brain-inspired feature to practical engineering levers (e.g., sparse MoE routing; event-camera pipelines; low-precision inference; local learning) and the responsibility benefits (e.g., energy efficiency, robustness under shift, accountability via edit locality, transparency via focus logs). Reportable metrics are % active units/inference (sparsity), entropy of expert usage (routing), energy per 1k inferences (event-driven), and calibration/abstention rates (interaction).

Cognitive/ Behavioral Feature	Biological / Cognitive Motivation	AI instantiation Examples	Reliability Payoffs	Responsible-AI principles reinforced	Reportable metric
Framing invariance	Human framing effects	Evaluate stability across gain/loss phrasing	Reduces susceptibility to wording; improves user trust	Fairness, Explainability, Accountability	δ recommendation rate across frames; CI on δ
Anchoring resilience	Anchoring bias	Inject irrelevant anchors; measure effect size	Prevents spurious numeric drift; safer estimates	Fairness, Robustness, Accountability	Anchor effect size (Cohen’s d) vs control; slope to anchor magnitude
Confirmation-challenge	Confirmation bias	Require retrieval of disconfirming evidence/ counterfactuals	Encourages balanced advice; mitigates echoing user priors	Fairness, Accountability, Transparency	% trials with counter-evidence surfaced; time-to-counterexample
Calibration & abstention	Confidence/ metacognition signals	Calibrated probabilities; defer/abstain under ambiguity	Fewer overconfident errors; safe escalation to humans	Robustness & safety, Human oversight, Transparency	ECE; selective risk at target coverage; abstain/deferral rate
Resource-rational interaction	Bounded rationality; speed–accuracy trade-off	“Fast vs. Sure” modes; progressive disclosure; workload-aware timing	Matches output to attention/time budgets; lowers error under load	Human agency & oversight, Robustness, Explainability	(Latency, accuracy, energy) triplet per mode; user-switch rate
Compositional generalization	Human-like few-shot structure learning	Few-shot recombination benchmarks; structure-aware curricula	Better generalization under data shift; lower retraining energy	Robustness, Efficiency	SCAN/COGS-style split accuracy; compositional OOD gap (ID→OOD δ); part-substitution success rate; edit-locality score after adding a new “part” concept
Predictive-coding deployment	Error-centric perception	Event-driven edge alerts; UIs show deltas not dumps	Saves compute/bandwidth; focuses human attention on change	Efficiency, Transparency, Human oversight	Bytes moved/layer; proportion of updates that are error-driven; energy per 1k inferences vs. standard baseline; false-alarm/miss rates on “surprise” detectors
Active perception & attention/ Working-memory limits	Saccades/foveation; selective attention	Glimpse networks; spatial transformers; auditable focus logs	Lower energy; auditable “what was looked at”; contestability	Transparency & explainability, Efficiency, Accountability	#glimpses per task; latency/accuracy/energy triplet at fixed budget; token/region-level focus logs; accuracy drop past WM budget; selective-abstention rate under overload

Table 3: Same as Table 2 but for neurobiological features

Neurobiological Feature	Biological / Cognitive Motivation	AI instantiation Examples	Reliability Payoffs	Responsible-AI principles reinforced	Reportable metric
Neurobiological Features					
Sparse activity	Sparse coding; metabolic cost of spikes	ReLU sparsity; magnitude pruning / lottery tickets; sparse Mixture of Experts routing	Fewer multiply-accumulate operations, smaller models; often better object-oriented design by reducing shortcut features	Efficiency, Robustness, Accountability/Auditability	% active units/inference; FLOPs/inference; entropy of expert usage; route length
Event-driven computation	Retina transmits changes; spikes	Spiking NNs; event-camera pipelines; neuro-morphic inference	Low-latency, low-power edge compute; process only salient events	Efficiency, Robustness, Societal/Environmental well-being	Energy/inference; time-to-first-token or frame; trigger precision/recall
Local learning	Hebbian plasticity; spike-timing-dependent plasticity	Direct/Feedback alignment; equilibrium propagation; e-prop for SNNs	On-device/online updates without global backprop; privacy and bandwidth wins	Privacy & data governance, Efficiency, Accountability	Bytes transferred/update; on-device vs central gradient steps; privacy budget (if DP)
Low-precision signals	Analog, variable neural responses	Quantization (8/4-bit), deep compression, distillation	Faster/cheaper inference, lower CO ₂ e with minimal accuracy loss	Efficiency, Societal/Environmental well-being	Latency/inference; accuracy drop vs FP16; energy/CO ₂ e delta
Redundancy reduction / predictive coding	Cortex emphasizes prediction errors	Predictive-coding networks; PC as local backprop approximation	Less data movement; local learning; energy savings	Efficiency, Transparency, Robustness	Activation sparsity; bytes moved/layer; error-driven update ratio
Dendritic computation	Compartmental nonlinearities; dendritic spikes	Dendrite-inspired units / compartmental multilayer perceptron neurons	Parameter efficiency; modular credit assignment; potential energy gains	Efficiency, Interpretability, Accountability	Parameters per task; gradient locality score; energy/accuracy Pareto point

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Neurobiological Feature	Biological / Cognitive Motivation	AI instantiation Examples	Reliability Payoffs	Responsible-AI principles reinforced	Reportable metric
Modularity & localized routing	Microcircuit architecture; cortical columns/motifs; hierarchical pathways	Mixture-of-Experts; conditional computation; dynamic routing	Activates needed experts for sparse floating-point operations; fault isolation; clearer ownership	Accountability, Efficiency, Robustness	Expert-activation trace; edit-locality score; % routed tokens
Recurrence & feedback	Ventral-stream loops; occlusion tolerance	ConvRNNs; recurrent/feedback blocks in CNNs/Transformers	More robust under occlusion/clutter; iterative, auditable stages	Robustness & safety, Interpretability	Accuracy on $-C/-P/-A$; iterations-to-convergence; intermediate-state logs
Early-vision front-ends	V1 Gabor filters; gain control; neuronal noise	V1-like front ends (e.g., VOneNet)	Boosts corruption robustness and brain alignment without extra training	Robustness, Interpretability	ImageNet- $C/-P$ deltas; Brain-Score/RSA alignment; clean-accuracy delta
Specialized substrates	Mixed analog/digital; sparse spikes	Neuromorphic chips (Loihi, TrueNorth, SpiNaker)	Orders-of-magnitude energy gains; on-chip learning	Efficiency, Societal/Environmental well-being	Joules/inference; throughput/Watt; training-on-chip yes/no